

Geotourism and Sustainable Development in Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark: A Quantitative and Thematic Analysis

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to evaluate the institutional maturity process of the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark by examining its quantitative indicators and thematic practices for the period 2018-2022. The research was designed using a mixed-methods approach, and data were obtained from the annual reports published by the Global Geoparks Network. Quantitative trends were analyzed through indicators such as staff, visitors, events, educational programs, and press releases, while thematic practices were examined under the themes of geoconservation, sustainability, education, strategic partnerships, and promotion. The findings indicate that the indicators remained stable during 2018-2019, declined in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and showed a notable recovery and transformation in both quantitative indicators and institutional management during 2021 and 2022. Geoconservation practices evolved from a protection-oriented approach to a proactive and visitor-centered infrastructure management model. Under the theme of sustainability, a participatory governance model was reinforced through local guide training, cooperative support, and online awareness programs. Educational activities were transferred to digital platforms, strategic partnerships diversified at both national and international levels, and promotional efforts became more effective through digitalization and enhanced media visibility. In conclusion, between 2018 and 2022, the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark has evolved into a sustainable geotourism model that integrates the themes of geoconservation, sustainability, education, cooperation, and promotion—simultaneously advancing heritage conservation, community participation, and local development.

Keywords: Geotourism, Sustainable Development, Geoconservation, UNESCO Global Geoparks, Kula-Salihli Geopark

Introduction

Geotourism is a form of sustainable tourism that focuses on experiencing the geological features of the Earth, promotes environmental and cultural understanding, appreciation, and conservation, and provides benefits at the local level (Dowling, 2010, 2013). Today, geotourism—considered an “emerging tourism niche”—remains in the early stages of commercial development in most countries, with geoparks playing a pioneering role in its advancement. Notably, geoparks actively engage local communities in the process through innovative strategies and geo-marketing practices. Through such innovative approaches, geoparks both stimulate the local economy and enhance public knowledge of geology. Furthermore, geopark administrations adopt a participatory governance model aligned with sustainable development goals by actively involving local communities in conservation

activities, environmental education programs, and tourism marketing initiatives (Torabi Farsani et al., 2011, p. 68).

UNESCO Global Geoparks are increasingly recognized worldwide as areas where conservation, sustainable development, and community engagement can be implemented in an integrated manner. These internationally significant sites are managed with a holistic approach encompassing conservation, education, and sustainable development. UNESCO began working with geoparks in 2001, and in 2004, the Global Geopark Network (GGN) was established in Paris. In 2015, at its 38th General Conference, UNESCO revised the status of geoparks, allowing for their international recognition under a dedicated UNESCO program. With the adoption of the Statute of the International Geosciences and Geoparks Programme, the concept of the UNESCO Global Geopark was formally established. The Kula-Salihli Geopark is Türkiye's first and only UNESCO Global Geopark (National Commission of UNESCO Türkiye, n.d.). Due to its natural, geological, cultural, and archaeological richness, it is one of Türkiye's most important areas for geotourism (Jeopark Municipalities Union, n.d.).

The aim of this research is to examine the statistical data of the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark for the years 2018-2022 and to thematically analyze the geotourism-focused practices carried out in the geopark during this period. Within this scope, the research analyzes quantitative trends over the five-year period (2018-2022) based on indicators such as the number of staff, visitors, events, school classes participating in geopark educational programs, and press releases. Additionally, the research evaluates the geotourism-focused practices implemented in the geopark within the themes of geoconservation, sustainability, education, strategic partnerships, and promotion, based on the same years. The literature on tourism in the research area is limited (Bahtiyar Sarı, 2025; Usta & Kırlar Can, 2021; Yürür & Akoğlan Kozak, 2018). This research is significant both for addressing this gap and for contributing to the literature with its unique subject matter.

Literature Review

Geotourism and Sustainable Development

Geotourism, through its “geo” component, concerns landscapes, landforms, fossil deposits, rocks, and minerals, which are evaluated within the scope of geology, geomorphology, and natural resources; it emphasizes understanding and appreciating the processes that shape these features. The tourism dimension involves visiting geosites for purposes such as recreation, aesthetic admiration, learning, and raising awareness. Such visits may include organized tours, thematic activities, and the development of accommodation facilities. Additionally, various practices exist for the planning and management of geosites. In this context, geotourism is defined as a distinct sub-sector within nature-based tourism (Newsome & Dowling, 2006, pp. 3-4).

Geotourism is a form of tourism that fundamentally aims to introduce and explain the Earth to tourists (Körbalta, 2018, p. 194). Initially defined solely as “geological tourism” as an environmentally innovative form of tourism, geotourism has gradually developed into a tourism approach focused on geology and landscape. Geotourism promotes tourism to geosites, the conservation of geological diversity, and the understanding of Earth sciences through appreciation and learning. This approach is implemented through activities such as visiting geological formations, using geo-trails and viewpoints, guided tours, geo-events, and supporting geosite visitor centers. Geotourists may consist of both independent travelers and group tourists, and they can visit natural or urban/built areas with geological attractions. In this respect, geotourism is distinguished from other nature-based tourism types that occur solely in natural areas (Dowling, 2013, p. 60).

Geotourism is considered a multidimensional phenomenon that goes beyond the mere conservation and promotion of geological features, encompassing interactions between local communities and visitors. This approach allows travelers to move freely and experience the sense of place, while ensuring that the value of host communities' culture, local products, and socio-economic structures is properly recognized and preserved. Accordingly, geotourism can be defined as a form of tourism that enhances the material well-being of local populations without disrupting traditional employment, cultural cohesion, or social balance (Torabi Farsani et al., 2012, p. 32).

Dowling (2011, p. 4) identifies the primary objectives of sustainable geotourism development as increasing awareness and understanding of the contributions geotourism can make to the environment, local communities, and the economy; promoting justice and equity in the geo-development process; enhancing the quality of life of host communities; providing visitors with a high-quality and authentic geological experience; and ensuring the conservation of geological heritage, which underpins these goals. In this context, geotourism is regarded as a holistic approach that not only promotes natural and geological heritage but also aims to conserve this heritage and actively involve local populations in the sustainable development process. Areas with geotourism value are categorized into two groups: those with high scientific value but limited visual appeal, and those with both high scientific and visual value. Today, the majority of geotourism activities take place within geoparks (Körbaltá, 2018, p. 194).

UNESCO Global Geoparks

Geoparks are areas in which geosites of the same or different types are collectively located, covering a space that is not small enough to be explored entirely on foot (Association for the Protection of Geological Heritage, 2003). UNESCO Global Geoparks are unique areas worldwide that offer visitors the opportunity to touch, explore, and connect with a part of the Earth's story. These sites, where extraordinary landscapes, places, and people converge, possess heritage values of international significance not only for geological reasons but also for archaeological, ecological, economic, historical, and cultural factors. Often associated with a globally recognized brand identity, these areas contribute to the development of sustainable tourism and support regional development under the leadership of local communities (European UNESCO Geoparks Network, 2025; Ólafsdóttir & Dowling, 2013).

UNESCO Global Geoparks are unique and unified geographical areas where sites and landscapes of international geological significance are managed with an integrated approach to conservation, education, and sustainable development. They are established through a bottom-up process that involves all relevant local and regional stakeholders and authorities in the area, such as landowners, community groups, tourism providers, indigenous populations, and local organizations. This process requires strong commitment from local communities, a robust long-term multi-stakeholder partnership supported by public and political backing, and the development of a comprehensive strategy that showcases and preserves the region's geological heritage while meeting the objectives of all community members (UNESCO, 2025a).

UNESCO Global Geoparks foster awareness of the importance of a region's geological heritage in both historical and contemporary contexts, encouraging local communities to take pride in and identify with their region. Through geotourism, new sources of income are generated while geological resources are preserved, and the creation of innovative local businesses, new employment opportunities, and high-quality educational programs is promoted. Currently, there are 229 UNESCO Global Geoparks across 50 countries. UNESCO Global Geoparks are structured not only at the national level but also at transnational and regional levels. Globally, there are five transnational UNESCO Global Geoparks, located across Austria-Slovenia, Belgium-Netherlands, Germany-Poland, Hungary-Slovakia, and

Ireland-the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland. In addition, there are four regional UNESCO Global Geopark networks operating in Asia, Europe, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Africa (UNESCO, 2025b).

The Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark in Türkiye, which constitutes the focus of this research, is a member of the European UNESCO Global Geoparks Network (EGN). The main aim of this network is to promote sustainable regional development, particularly through the advancement of geotourism, by utilizing geological heritage. The network regularly evaluates the activities and services of its member geoparks to maintain the “European Geopark” brand as a standard of high-quality geotourism. Member geoparks are required to prepare a management and action plan that encompasses elements such as heritage identification, conservation, interpretation, environmental education, promotion, support for local enterprises, and international cooperation (European Geoparks Network, n.d.). Table 1 presents the geoparks in the European UNESCO Geoparks Network and their distribution. As shown in the table, the European UNESCO Geoparks Network comprises a total of 113 geoparks, with Spain ranking first with 18 geoparks (UNESCO, 2025b).

Table 1. Geoparks in the European UNESCO Geoparks Network

No.	Country	Name of Geopark
1	Austria	Ore of the Alps (1), Styrian Eisenwurzen (2)
2	Austria-Slovenia	Karavanken/Karawanke (1)
3	Belgium	Famenne-Ardenne (1)
4	Belgium-Kingdom of the Netherlands	Schelde Delta (1)
5	Croatia	Biokovo-Imotski Lakes (1), Papuk (2), Vis Archipelago (3)
6	Cyprus	Troodos (1)
7	Czechia	Bohemian Paradise (1)
8	Denmark	Odsherred (1), The South Fyn Archipelago (2), Vestjylland (3)
9	Finland	Impact Crater Lake-Lappajärvi (1), Lauhanvuori-Haemeen kangas (2), Rokua (3), Saimaa (4), Salpausselkä (5)
10	France	Armorique (1), Beaujolais (2), Causses du Quercy (3), Chablais (4), Haute-Provence (5), Luberon (6), Massif des Bauges (7), Monts d'Ardèche (8), Normandie-Maine (9)
11	Germany	Bergstraße-Odenwald (1), Harz, Braunschweiger Land (2), Swabian Alb (3), TERRA.vita (4), Vulkaneifel (5), Thuringia Inselsberg -Drei Gleichen (6), Ries (7)
12	Germany-Poland	Muskauer Faltenbogen / Łuk Mużakowa (1)
13	Greece	Chelmos Vouraikos (1), Grevena-Kozani (2), Kefalonia-Ithaca (3), Lavreotiki (4), Lesvos Island (5), Meteora Pyli (6), Psiloritis (7), Sitia (8), Vikos-Aoos (9)
14	Hungary	Bakony-Balaton (1), Bükk Region (2)
15	Hungary-Slovakia	Novohrad-Nógrád (1)
16	Iceland	Katla (1), Reykjanes (2)
17	Ireland	Burren & Cliffs of Moher (1), Copper Coast (2)
18	Ireland & United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Cuilcagh Lakelands (1)
19	Italy	Adamello-Brenta (1), Alpi Apuane (2), Aspromonte (3), Beigua (4), Cilento, Vallo di Diano e Alburni (5), Madonie (6), Maiella

		(7), MurGEopark (8), Pollino (9), Rocca di Cerere (10), Sesia Val Grande (11), Tuscan Mining Park (12)
20	Luxembourg	Mëllerdall (1)
21	Kingdom of the Netherlands	De Hondsrug (1)
22	Norway	Gea Norvegica (1), Magma (2), Sunnhordland (3), The Fjord Coast (4), Trollfjell (5)
23	Poland	Holy Cross Mountains (1), Land of Extinct Volcanoes (2)
24	Portugal	Azores (1), Arouca (2), Estrela (3), Naturtejo (4), Oeste (5), Terras de Cavaleiros (6)
25	Romania	Buzău Land (1), Hațeg (2)
26	Russian Federation	Yangan-Tau (1)
27	Serbia	Djerdap (1)
28	Slovenia	Idrija (1)
29	Spain	Basque Coast (1), Cabo de Gata-Níjar (2), Cabo Ortegal (3), Calatrava Volcanoes. Ciudad Real (4), Central Catalonia (5), Costa Quebrada (6), Courel Mountains (7), El Hierro (8), Granada (9), Lanzarote and Chinijo Islands (10), Las Loras (11), Maestrazgo (12), Molina-Alto Tajo (13), Origenes (14), Sierra Morena de Sevilla (15), Sierras Subbéticas (16), Sobrarbe-Pirineos (17), Villuercas Ibores Jara (18)
30	Sweden	Platåbergens (1)
31	Türkiye	Kula Salihli (1)
32	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	Arran (1), Black Country (2), English Riviera (3), Fforest Fawr (4), GeoMôn (5), Mourne Gullion Strangford (6), North Pennines AONB (7), North-West Highlands (8), Shetland (9)

Source: UNESCO, 2025b.

Methodology

Research Area: Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark

The Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark is located in the central part of the Gediz Graben and the western section of the Inner Western Anatolia Plateaus. The geopark encompasses the entire administrative boundaries of the Kula and Salihli districts of Manisa Province and covers a total area of 2,320 km². Situated in a region where crustal movements are frequent and significant, the Kula-Salihli Geopark exhibits a geologically and tectonically complex and geomorphologically diverse structure. The geopark contains evidence of more than 300 million years of Earth's history, ranging from Paleozoic metamorphic rocks (such as schist and gneiss) to prehistoric volcanic eruptions, making it remarkably rich in geodiversity. The Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark is also one of the youngest volcanic areas in Türkiye. Throughout history, the geopark area has hosted numerous civilizations. Sardis, the capital of the Lydian Kingdom—where money was first minted and used under state guarantee—is located within the boundaries of the geopark. Due to its natural, cultural, and archaeological wealth, the Kula-Salihli Geopark represents one of the most significant areas for geotourism in Türkiye (Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark, n.d.-a). Figure 1 shows the location of the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark. The geopark contains 73 registered geosites (Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark, n.d.-b). Table 2 presents some of the natural, cultural, and geoarchaeological geosites within the geopark.

Figure 1. The Location of the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark
Source: European Geoparks Network, n.d.; Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark, n.d.-b.

Table 2. Some Natural, Cultural, and Geoarchaeological Geosites in the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark

Natural Geosites	Cultural Geosites	Geoarchaeological Geosites
Kaplan Divlit Volcano Cones	Kurşunlu Hot Springs	Gymnasium
Suuçtu Waterfall	Maiden Bridge	Tabala Castle Mesa Structure and Roman Castle
The Gediz Graben	The Mud Bath Hot Springs	Thermaï Thessos Hot Springs and Rock Sculptures
Tmolos Deposits	Hoca Seyfeddin Bridge	Prehistoric Rock Paintings
Evciler Shist	Damatlı Village	The Thousand Hills
Sandal Divlit	Village Architecture and Cisterns in Old Kollyda (Gölde)	Elekçitepe Rock Tombs
Acısu Ophiolites	Kemer Village	Sardis and the Temple of Artemis
Çakırca Basalt Columns	Viticulture	
Üfürük Geothermal Resource	Gökeyüp Pottery	
Hydrothermal Alteration of Tmolos Deposits	Historical Kula Houses	
Adala Volcanic Canyon	Tomb of Tabduk Emre and Yunus Emre-Carullah Bin Suleiman Mosque	
Marmara Lake		
Kısık River Ancient Quarry		
Kurşunlu Valley		
Kula Fairy Chimneys		

Tabak River Potholes		
Kula Volkanic Park		

Source: Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark, n.d.-c.

Data Collection and Analysis

This research was designed based on a mixed-method approach. Using both quantitative and qualitative data, it comprehensively examined the geotourism and sustainable development processes in the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark. The data were obtained from the most recent five-year (2018-2022) reports of the Global Geoparks Network related to the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark. In the quantitative part of the research, the number of staff, visitors, events, school classes participating in educational programs, and press releases during this five-year period were compiled and presented. In the qualitative part, a thematic analysis of the documents was conducted to assess the status of geoconservation, sustainability, education, strategic partnerships, and promotional practices during the same period.

Results

Statistical Data

Table 3 presents the number of staff, visitors, events, educational programs, and press releases of the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022. Upon examining the table, it is observed that the number of staff increased to 14, particularly from 2020 onward, while the number of geologists remained constant at 4. Visitor numbers were around 90,000 in 2018 and 2019, dropped to 32,400 in 2020 due to the pandemic, and reached their highest level of 147,000 in 2022. The number of events followed a similar trend, decreasing to 27 in 2020 and peaking at 63 in 2022. The number of school classes participating in educational programs was at its lowest in 2020 (4 classes) and increased to 19 classes in 2022. The number of press releases, which was 6 in 2019, rose to 92 in 2022, indicating a significant increase in the geopark's media visibility.

Table 3. Number of Staff, Visitors, Events, Educational Programs, and Press Releases at Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022

Year	Number of Staff	Number of Visitors	Number of Events	Number of School Classes Participating in Geopark Educational Programmes	Number of Press Releases
2018	12 (2 of which are geologists)	91.000	30	40	85
2019	12 (4 of them geologists)	90.000	43	12	6
2020	12 (4 of them geologists)	32.400	27	4	39
2021	12 (4 of them geologists)	78.220	47	9	63
2022	12 (4 of them geologists)	147.000	63	19	92

Results of Thematic Analysis

Table 4 presents the geoconservation practices carried out at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022, categorized according to their main and sub-themes. As shown in the table, in 2018, three personnel were employed for the protection of geological heritage. In 2019, this approach continued with the appointment of three new wardens, and seminars were organized for primary school students under the theme of environmental awareness. In 2020, the employment of security personnel continued within

the scope of conservation management, while activities related to visitor safety and environmental awareness were conducted under the infrastructure management and community engagement themes. No data is available for this topic in 2021. In 2022, geoconservation activities were carried out under the theme of infrastructure management, including the replacement of signs to improve visitor information, visitor safety, and visitor experience, maintenance of walking trails, and the construction of new routes.

Table 4. Geoconservation Practices Implemented at Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022

Year	Main Theme	Sub-Theme 1	Sub-Theme 2	Explanation
2018	Geoconservation	Conservation Management	Protection of Geological Heritage	Three new personnel were employed for the monitoring of geoconservation activities and the protection of geosites
2019	Geoconservation	Conservation Management	Protection of Geological Heritage	Three new rangers were employed to ensure the protection of the geopark and to conduct patrol operations.
		Conservation Management	Environmental Awareness	In October 2019, seminars were organized for primary school students on how to keep the geopark clean and protected.
2020	Geoconservation	Conservation Management	Protection of Geological Heritage	Two rangers were employed to ensure the security of the geopark.
		Infrastructure Management	Visitor Safety	The damaged infrastructure within the geopark was repaired, and maintenance work was carried out on the existing facilities.
		Community Participation	Environmental Awareness	A litter collection event was organized in collaboration with several non-governmental organizations to enhance the recognition of the geopark and raise awareness among children.
2021	No Data	No Data	No Data	No Data
2022	Geoconservation	Infrastructure Management	Visitor Information	Damaged signs and directional boards were replaced with new ones, and several new information panels were installed within the geopark area.
		Infrastructure Management	Visitor Safety	Regular maintenance and repairs were carried out on the walking trails and railings within the area.
		Infrastructure Management	Visitor Experience	New walking trails were constructed to allow visitors to better explore the geosites.

Table 5 presents the sustainability practices implemented at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022, categorized according to their main and sub-themes. As shown in the table, in 2018, collaborations were established with tourism enterprises to

promote sustainable tourism. Within the scope of academic cooperation, a protocol was signed to determine the geopark’s tourism potential and stakeholder attitudes, and a project agreement was made to assess the cultural and environmental awareness of the local community. In 2019, fifty local guides were trained, and geotourism orientation seminars were organized in schools to support tourism development. In 2020, an awareness-raising magazine targeting children was prepared. In 2021, educational programs on sustainable tourism were delivered to the local community; financial support was provided to individuals and organizations seeking income generation; and online education programs on sustainable development were conducted in selected schools. In 2022, education on sustainable development was provided to various age groups, from primary school to university; financial support was offered to partner organizations and cooperatives; online training sessions on sustainable development goals were organized in schools and public forums; and a seminar on cultural heritage was conducted.

Table 5. Sustainability Practices Implemented at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022

Year	Main Theme	Sub-Theme 1	Sub-Theme 2	Explanation
2018	Sustainability	Collaboration with Tourism Enterprises	Tourism Development	Partnership agreements were established with tourism-related enterprises (hotels, restaurants, souvenir shops) to promote sustainable tourism.
		Academic Collaboration	Research and Planning	A protocol was signed with Dr. Cemali Sarı from the Department of Geography at Akdeniz University to determine the tourism potential of Kula Geopark and stakeholder attitudes.
		Academic Collaboration	Cultural and Environmental Awareness	A project agreement was made with Prof. Mustafa Ertürk to assess the cultural and ecological awareness of the local community regarding the geopark.
2019	Sustainability	Guidance and Human Resources	Tourism Development	Fifty new local guides were trained to promote sustainable tourism.
		Education	Geotourism Education	Between September and December, orientation seminars on geotourism were organized in schools in the Kula district.
2020	Sustainability	Education	Children’s Magazine	A children’s magazine was prepared to raise awareness among children and increase the visibility of the geopark.
2021	Sustainability	Education	Local Community Education	Education on the geopark and conservation was provided to the local community within the context of sustainable tourism.
		Financial	Monetary	Financial support was provided

		Support	Support	to local residents, associations, and cooperatives seeking income generation.
		Education	Sustainable Development	Online educational programs on “The Importance of Geoparks for Sustainable Development” were organized in selected schools.
2022	Sustainability	Education	Sustainable Development	Education on the concept of sustainable development was provided to students of various age groups, from primary school to university.
		Financial Support	Monetary Support	The Geopark Municipalities Union provided financial support to partner organizations and cooperatives.
		Education	Sustainable Development	Online training sessions on sustainable development goals were conducted in selected schools and public forums.
		Education	Cultural Heritage	Dr. Serdar Aytaç, Coordinator of the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark, delivered an online seminar presentation entitled “Geoparks and the Place of Cultural Heritage in Geoparks”.

Table 6 presents the educational activities implemented at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022, categorized according to main and sub-themes. As shown in the table, in 2018, under the theme of “Promotion and Awareness”, geopark promotional tours were organized for tourism companies and guides; under “Vocational Training”, seminars on geoparks and tourism were provided to tourism enterprises; under “Stakeholder Training”, stakeholders received training on the geopark; and under “School Education”, primary school students were informed about natural disasters. In 2019, this approach was continued, and “School Education” seminars on types of natural disasters and protection methods were conducted in two schools in Kula. In 2020, under “Online Education”, a two-day seminar on climate change was held on October 13 (International Day for Disaster Risk Reduction); additionally, under “School Education”, a seminar on the formation and importance of mountains was delivered to students on December 11 (International Mountain Day). In 2021, both “Online Education” and “School Education” formats were used to provide primary and secondary school students with training on the importance of water and geoconservation; “Online Education” also included activities related to special days, and a presentation on sustainable development and the role of geographers was delivered. In 2022, under “School Education”, four face-to-face sessions on water and geoconservation were provided to students; additionally, “Online Education” activities continued in connection with special days.

Table 6. Educational Activities Implemented at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark Between 2018 and 2022

Year	Main Theme	Sub-Theme 1	Sub-Theme 2	Explanation
2018	Education	Promotion and Awareness	Geopark Promotional Tours	Geopark tours were organized to promote the geopark to tourism companies in neighboring provinces and districts.
		Promotion and Awareness	Geopark Promotional Tours	Geopark tours were organized for tourism guides working in the region to promote the geopark.
		Vocational Training	Geopark and Tourism	A training seminar on geoparks and tourism was delivered to tourism enterprises in the surrounding provinces.
		Stakeholder Training	Geopark Orientation	Stakeholders of the Kula Global Geopark were provided with training on the geopark.
		School Education	Natural Disasters	Primary school students were provided with education on natural disasters.
2019	Education	School Education	Natural Disasters	Two informative seminars on types of natural disasters and protection methods were organized in two schools in Kula.
2020	Education	Online Education	Climate Change	A two-day online seminar on climate change was organized as part of International Day for Disaster Risk Reduction on October 13.
		School Education	Formation and Importance of Mountains	A seminar on the formation and importance of mountains was organized as part of International Mountain Day on December 11.
2021	Education	Online Education	Water and Geoconservation	Two online educational sessions on the importance of water and geoconservation were provided to primary and secondary school students.
		School Education	Water and Geoconservation	Two face-to-face educational sessions on the importance of water and geoconservation were provided to primary and secondary school students.
		Online Education	Special Days	Online educational sessions were organized as part of International Mountain Day on December 11, International Disaster Risk Reduction Day on October 13, and Geoparks Week from May 22 to

				June 7.
		Online Education	Sustainable Development and Geographers' Place	Coordinator Dr. A. Serdar Aytac delivered an online presentation entitled "Geoparks as a Device of Sustainable Development and the Place of Geographers in the Geopark".
2022	Education	School Education	Water and Geoconservation	Four face-to-face educational sessions on the importance of water and geoconservation were provided to primary and secondary school students.
		Online Education	Special Days	Online educational sessions were organized as part of International Mountain Day on December 11, International Disaster Risk Reduction Day on October 13, and Geoparks Week from May 22 to June 7.

Table 7 presents the strategic partnership practices carried out at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022, categorized according to their main and sub-themes. As shown in the table, in 2018, under National Collaboration, a corporate promotion protocol was signed with the Anemon Hotels chain, ensuring the Geopark's promotion in 32 Anemon hotels across Türkiye. In 2019, under International Collaboration, a Sister Geopark Protocol was signed with Qeshm Island Geopark in Iran, while under National Collaboration, numerous partnership protocols were established with local businesses. In 2020, National Collaboration included the establishment of a corporate partnership with the Turkish Geomorphology Association and geological research collaboration with the Manisa Provincial Directorate of Culture; International Collaboration involved an online meeting regarding the European Union Climate Change Project; and Academic Collaboration supported a TÜBİTAK project. In 2021, under International Collaboration, international Geopark promotion activities with multinational participation were organized; Educational Collaboration provided student orientation and information sessions; National Collaboration offered technical support to provinces conducting geopark establishment efforts; and Event Collaboration included the organization of a bicycle festival. In 2022, National Collaboration involved signing protocols with tourism companies and cooperatives and organizing environmental awareness activities; Educational Collaboration encompassed summer school trainings and teacher training programs; International Collaboration included the VR@Geoparks and Erasmus+ projects; and Event Collaboration covered participation in the Geology and Geomorphology Festivals.

Table 7. Strategic Partnership Activities Implemented at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark Between 2018 and 2022

Year	Main Theme	Sub-Theme 1	Sub-Theme 2	Explanation
2018	Strategic Partnership	National Collaboration	Institutional Promotion Protocol	A protocol was signed with the Anemon Hotels chain and within this scope, the Kula Geopark will be promoted in 32 Anemon hotels across Türkiye.
2019	Strategic	International	Sister Geopark	A Sister Geopark Protocol was

	Partnership	Collaboration	Protocol	signed with the Qeshm Island Geopark in Iran, establishing international collaboration.
		National Collaboration	Local Partnership Protocol	Strategic partnership protocols were signed between the Geopark and six restaurants, two associations, five hotels, and two souvenir shops.
2020	Strategic Partnership	National Collaboration	Corporate Partnership	A corporate partnership was established for the Geomorphology Symposium, planned to be organized in collaboration with the Turkish Geomorphology Association.
		National Collaboration	Geological Research Collaboration	Collaboration was conducted with the Manisa Provincial Directorate of Culture to identify new geological sites within the boundaries of the Geopark.
		International Collaboration	Climate Change Project	An online meeting was held with Assoc. Prof. Bülent Arıkan at ITU Eurasia Institute of Earth Sciences regarding the European Union project on Global Climate Change.
		Academic Collaboration	TÜBİTAK Project	A collaboration meeting was held for the TÜBİTAK project led by Assoc. Prof. Özgür Karaoğlu.
2021	Strategic Partnership	International Collaboration	Geopark Promotion	A one-week event was organized in the Kula and Salihli districts with participants from Türkiye, Hungary, Poland, Spain, and Romania, focusing on the significance of the Geopark in terms of international relations, and important geosites were visited and explained.
		Educational Collaboration	Student Orientation	Approximately 100 students visited the Geopark and were informed about the Geopark, UNESCO Global Geoparks, geoconservation, and sustainable environmental practices.
		International Collaboration	Geopark Promotion	Visitors from Italy, North Macedonia, Poland, and Romania were provided with information about the Geopark, and important geosites were toured.
		National Collaboration	Geopark Establishment	Individuals involved in geopark establishment efforts in

			Activities	Kastamonu, Denizli, Nevşehir, and Balıkesir visited the Geopark at different times, important geosites were toured, and technical support was provided regarding the application processes.
		Event Collaboration	Bicycle Festival	A two-day bicycle festival was organized in collaboration with the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark and the Manisa Cycling Club. Fifty participants attended the event, and the Mayor and District Governor also joined the activities in the Geopark.
2022	Strategic Partnership	National Collaboration	Protocol with Tourism Companies and Cooperatives	Strategic partnership protocols were signed with tourism companies, restaurants, hotels, associations, and cooperatives located both within and outside the boundaries of the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark.
		Educational Collaboration	Summer School Trainings	In collaboration with the municipalities within the Geopark boundaries, students in summer schools were provided with training on “What is Geopark and the Importance of Geopark”.
		International Collaboration	VR@Geoparks Project	An international project called VR@Geoparks was conducted with the participation of Poland, Portugal, Hungary, Croatia, Türkiye, and Italy.
		Educational Collaboration	Teacher Training	A TÜBİTAK training, organized within the scope of the “Earth Sciences Education 5” program in the Çürüksu Basin and with the Geopark as a partner, was conducted. Forty teachers participated in the training.
		International Collaboration	Erasmus+ Project	The Geopark was introduced to students from the Czechia and Italy through the Erasmus+ KA210 project titled “Environment and Geoparks”, in which it participated as a partner.
		Event Collaboration	Geology Festival	Participation in the Geology Festival (JEOfEST), organized for the first time in Türkiye, was made possible through the

				established collaboration.
		National Collaboration	Geomorphology Festival	The International Geomorphology Festival was organized at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark in collaboration with the Geomorphology Association.
		National Collaboration	Environmental Awareness	A cleanup event was organized in collaboration with several non-governmental organizations to raise awareness about the Geopark.

Table 8 presents the promotional activities carried out at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022, categorized by main and sub-themes. As shown in the table, in 2018, promotional activities were primarily conducted through media and digital platforms; a documentary was produced, and the geopark was promoted on national radio and television channels. In 2019, promotional activities diversified: participation in national and international meetings was ensured, four new documentaries were produced, an Android mobile application for visitors was developed, promotional and directional panels were placed on main roads, and the geopark’s representation was strengthened through one academic meeting and one workshop. In 2020, activities focused on digitalization and accessibility: a Turkish and English website was designed, a virtual art gallery was created, cycling and walking routes were defined, an online seminar was organized, participation in an international conference was ensured, radio and TV programs and brochures were prepared, attendance and panel presentations were made at UNESCO meetings, teachers were informed, and an open-air fashion show was held at Kula Divlit Volcanic Park. In 2021, international representation and community engagement were emphasized: participation in international meetings was ensured, online training was provided to the public, visibility was increased through social media and promotional videos, TV interviews were conducted, environmental activities (tree planting, lavender harvesting) were organized, and visitors were informed. In 2022, promotional activities were expanded around education, digital platforms, and institutional collaboration: visitors were provided with information and education, school programs and student briefings were conducted, sustainable development training was organized, participation in meetings was ensured, project partnerships were developed, promotion was carried out through traditional media and digital platforms, informative presentations were delivered during environmental activities, and an article on the volcanic areas of Kula-Salihli Geopark was submitted for publication.

Table 8. Promotional Activities Conducted at the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark between 2018 and 2022

Year	Main Theme	Sub-Theme 1	Sub-Theme 2	Explanation
2018	Promotion	Media and Digital Promotion	Documentary	A documentary was produced to promote the Geopark on national and international platforms.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Radio and Television	The Geopark was promoted on several national radio and television channels.
2019	Promotion	Meeting Participation	National Meeting	The Geopark was promoted at the Aegean Region

				Development Meeting held in Ankara.
		Meeting Participation	International Meeting	The new Geopark was introduced at the 43rd European Geoparks Network Coordination Meeting in Aalen, Germany.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Mobile Application	An Android application for visitors to the Kula-Salihli Geopark was made available.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Documentary	Four new documentaries were prepared to promote the Geopark.
		Infrastructure and Physical Promotion	Promotional Panels	New promotional and directional panels have been installed along the main roads crossing the Geopark.
		Meeting Participation	Academic Meeting	Geopark staff participated in the meeting held in Tunceli.
		Meeting Participation	Workshop	The Geopark was promoted at the workshop held at Pamukkale University.
2020	Promotion	Media and Digital Promotion	Website	A new website has been designed for the geopark in both Turkish and English.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Virtual Art Gallery	A virtual art gallery was created on the website to encourage online participation.
		Infrastructure and Physical Promotion	Tour Routes	New cycling and hiking routes have been designated within the geopark area.
		Education	Online Seminar	An online geopark seminar was organized in collaboration with TMMOB (The Chamber of Geological Engineers of Türkiye).
		Meeting Participation	International Conference	The geopark coordinators participated in the Oxford Geoheritage Virtual Conference.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Article	An article titled “Early Pleistocene Underwater Volcanism in Gediz Valley: Kavtepe-Kula Volcanic

				Region” has been published.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Radio Program	A radio interview about the geopark was given by Prof. Dr. Tuncer Demir.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Brochures	New informative brochures about the geopark have been prepared.
		Media and Digital Promotion	TV Program	The President of the Union of Municipalities participated in a TV program in Manisa and gave an informative talk about the geopark.
		Meeting Participation	UNESCO Meeting	Geopark members participated in the Online UNESCO Grand Meeting Conference.
		Meeting Participation	Panels	The geopark coordinators gave presentations at two separate geopark panels.
		Education	Teacher Information	As part of the TÜBİTAK Nature Education Activity, teachers visiting the geopark were given an introduction to the geopark.
		Show	Fashion Show	An outdoor fashion show was organized on clothing at the Kula Divlit Volcanic Park.
2021	Promotion	Meeting Participation	International Meeting	The geopark coordinators participated in an international meeting organized by Batken University in Kazakhstan.
		Education	Public Education	The geopark has offered public online education on natural disasters and geological conservation.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Media Platforms and Photo/Video	To increase the visibility of the geopark, photos and promotional videos were taken and published on social media and various platforms.
		Media and Digital Promotion	TV Interviews	Interviews about the geopark were given to several national TV channels.
		Environmental	Tree Planting	Approximately 300

		Event		different tree species have been planted within the geopark boundaries to emphasize the importance of nature.
		Environmental Event	Lavender Harvest	The Lavender Harvest event was supported in collaboration with the Women's Cooperative and Kula Municipality, and a geopark tour was organized for the visitors.
		Education	Visitor Information	At different times, various activities have been organized for tourists and individuals visiting the geopark to highlight the importance of nature conservation.
2022	Promotion	Information and Education	Visitor Information/Education	Visitors of all ages to the geopark were provided with information about the geopark, and some on-site educational activities were organized.
		Education	School Education	Various educational activities on different topics have been organized in many schools.
		Meeting Participation	International Meeting	Representatives of the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark participated in the meetings.
		Information and Education	Student Information/Education	Students attending summer sports schools were provided with informational education about the geopark.
		Meeting Participation	Online Meetings	Participation was provided in various online meetings on the geopark and sustainable development.
		Education	Geopark and Sustainable Development Education	Education has been provided on geopark and sustainable development topics.
		Promotional Collaboratio	Project Partnerships	Partnerships have been established through various projects to promote the

				geopark both nationally and internationally.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Traditional Media	Geopark promotional activities have been carried out on TV, radio, and in newspapers.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Digital Platform	Various promotional videos were recorded and shared on social media platforms.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Digital Platform	Promotional activities have been carried out on digital platforms such as social media and the website.
		Meeting Participation	Congress, Painting Stand, and Brochures	A painting stand was opened at the congress held in Salihli and brochures about the geopark were distributed to the participants.
		Environmental Event and Education	Tree Planting and Information	The Kula-Salihli Geopark participated in a tree planting event and gave presentations on nature conservation and global climate change.
		Meeting Participation	Local Meeting	Participation was ensured in the meeting held in Manisa, where an informative presentation about the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark was given; the meeting was attended by many high-level executives.
		Media and Digital Promotion	Article	An article on the volcanic areas of Kula-Salihli Geopark was submitted to the magazine Geoparks in Volcanic Areas in Europe.

Conclusion and Discussion

In this research, the institutional maturity process of the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark during the 2018-2022 period was evaluated through both quantitative and thematic analyses. The quantitative findings of the research indicate that the COVID-19 pandemic reduced the number of visitors to 32,400, the number of events to 27, and the number of school classes participating in educational programs to 4 in 2020. However, the recovery that began in 2021 led to historic peaks in 2022, with 147,000 visitors, 63 events, and 92 press releases; the staff structure maintained its stability even during the crisis, forming the foundation of institutional resilience. Yet the truly critical aspect is the qualitative transformation behind this quantitative recovery. The thematic analyses of this research reveal that this recovery was made possible by the geopark management systematically

integrating and diversifying its conservation, education, collaboration, and promotion strategies around the principles of sustainable development.

The research data indicate that the understanding of geoconservation has evolved from a static preservation approach to a proactive infrastructure management focused on visitor experience and safety. Sustainability practices, local guide training, cooperative support, and comprehensive educational programs have emphasized revitalizing the local economy. This directly aligns with Dowling's (2013) principle of sustainable geotourism, which highlights the "support of local socio-economic development" as a cornerstone. This research documents how this theoretically emphasized principle has been translated into concrete practices in the geopark under investigation.

Similarly, the transfer and diversification of educational and promotional activities to digital platforms have enhanced the resilience of the geopark and expanded its reach to a global scale. Strategic partnerships have developed into a multi-layered structure, spanning from local collaborations to international project networks. These findings provide concrete evidence of Yürür and Akoğlan Kozak's (2018) emphasis on a "strong governance model". This research demonstrates that the model is built upon a multi-stakeholder and flexible collaboration network.

Another significant finding of the research is the geopark's capacity to transform potential risks into opportunities. Environmental threats highlighted by Usta and Kırlar Can (2021) are, as evidenced in the data of this research, managed through increased environmental education and awareness activities; meanwhile, the cultural heritage potential emphasized by Bahtiyar Sarı (2025) is leveraged for the economy through events that showcase local values, such as lavender harvesting and cycling festivals.

In conclusion, the findings of this research demonstrate that over the five-year period, the Kula-Salihli UNESCO Global Geopark has evolved beyond being merely a geological heritage site, moving toward a sustainable and resilient model situated at the intersection of education, participatory governance, economic development, and institutional networking. This research clearly shows that the success of a geopark depends not only on its geological resources but also on the extent to which it can develop the surrounding social, economic, and managerial ecosystem.

Based on the findings and scope of this research, the following recommendations have been developed for both geopark management and future academic research:

Recommendations for Geopark Management

- **Institutionalization of digitalization:** Geopark management should institutionalize digitalization, online education, and promotional practices, particularly to ensure continuity of activities during crises. These applications, which accelerated after 2020, have the potential to expand accessibility and impact.
- **Participatory management models:** Mechanisms that enable active participation of local communities and stakeholders should be developed. This approach aligns with sustainability and strategic partnership practices observed in guide training, cooperative support, and stakeholder collaborations.
- **Strengthening international networks:** Diversifying strategic partnerships and increasing collaboration with international networks will enhance knowledge and experience sharing and boost the geopark's global visibility. The findings indicate positive momentum in this regard during the 2018-2022 period.
- **Comprehensive education and promotion strategy:** Educational, promotional, and awareness-raising activities should be conducted within a holistic strategy framework. Integrating online seminars, school-based activities, and thematic trainings will enable geotourism to contribute more effectively to sustainable development goals.

Recommendations for Future Research

- Since this research relied on secondary data, future research could employ qualitative data collection methods such as in-depth interviews, focus groups, or surveys of visitors and local communities to examine the social impacts of the geopark in greater detail.
- Comparative studies of different UNESCO Global Geoparks could help identify best practices and inform policy development.
- Long-term monitoring studies could evaluate the impacts of the geopark on the local economy, employment, environmental awareness, and regional development.
- Micro-level analyses focusing on geotourism experiences, visitor satisfaction, and sustainable tourism indicators could assist in developing measurable performance criteria for geopark management.

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